

Modeling hotel room pricing: A multi-country analysis

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Abstract

In the current tourism landscape, pricing decisions reemerge as a key concern for hoteliers. This study examines the impact of specific factors associated with hotels, customers' experience, and competition on hotel pricing in different countries. Certain features of market behavior can distort expected prices, such as asymmetric information, differences in hotel categorization, hotels spatial concentration or electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM). In order to understand the determinants of pricing and to obtain a complete characterization of them, the present study applies quantile regression to the prices of a sample of 3,800 hotels located in France, Spain, Italy and the United Kingdom. Results show the heterogeneity of the effects of hotel category, country location, eWOM and hotel competitive intensity across different price levels. Also, hotels concentration proves to have a generally positive effect on price, confirming positive effects of spatial concentration.

Keywords:

Hotels; Pricing; Spatial concentration; Category; eWOM; Quantile regression; Multi-country; Europe

1. Introduction

The objective of this study is to deepen the understanding of hotel pricing decisions by analyzing heterogeneous effects of hotel's characteristics, customers' experience, competition and country on fixed prices. A quantile regression model is used based on hotels from four countries.

The present work can be justified by several reasons. Firstly, at a conceptual level, the widespread use of dynamic pricing strategies (Abrate and Viglia, 2016) produces incentives to understand the price tactics of every hotel on an individual basis, increasing traditional properties of flexibility and utility of price in marketing programs, such as promotions (Abrate et al., 2012; Tanford et al., 2012), yield management (Emeksiz et al., 2006), lodging choice (Kim and Park, 2017), or customer satisfaction (Radojevic et al., 2015). Additionally, the vast development of multichannel strategies in hotels has led to the implementation of price changes more quickly than in conventional environments, requiring more intense and frequent management (Beritelli and Schegg, 2016; Toh et al., 2011).

Second, hotel pricing models incorporate category as an apparent unbiased signal of services selection and establishment quality based on regional regulations (Becerra et al., 2013). Although it offers the advantage of summarizing into an indicator an entire set of specific attributes (Azzopardi and Nash, 2013), several issues question category as an unbiased predictor. For example, hotel chains display problems associated with specific asymmetric information (Akerlof, 1970) and tourists have limited information about future prices and room availability (Chen and Schwartz, 2006). It has been verified that ranking by quality may not correspond to categories (López-Fernández and Serrano-Bedia, 2004). In particular, different regional and national regulations for hotel categorization are a source of heterogeneity that deteriorates its value as a standard quality signal (Nuñez-Serrano et al., 2014). What is more, many hotels draw on additional strategies to communicate their quality and service levels (Nicolau and Sellers, 2010). To understand the behavior of the category as a determinant signal of room price, we intend to evaluate its effect for different price levels and different countries.

Third, further hedonic modeling, pricing competition has basically been addressed from a differentiation perspective, yielding a negative main effect, but one which is not conclusive because it is conditioned to the type of moderator used (Becerra et al., 2013). However, evidence of divergence does exist. On the one hand, some hotels follow a price parity strategy to attract customers (Toh et al., 2011), avoiding a race to the bottom in room price. Also, from the spatial concentration perspective, the derived effect from competition can be positive. More specifically, the Central Place Theory (CPT) (King, 1984) postulates the existence of a concentration effect since economic activities are prone to cluster together in specific market areas. As a consequence, Daniels (2007) describes the relationship between the size of the available tourist activities in one place and the economic impact on each. However, spatial concentration effect on the price set by hotels has not been tested.

Fourth, the widespread use of social networks in C2C and B2C fields through comments and online rankings has shown its efficacy for explaining pricing (Yadav and Pavlou, 2014). From a demand perspective, the generalization of price information availability on the Internet has increased knowledge about hotel prices and, therefore, changed customers' evaluations (Noone and Mattila, 2009). Particular attention has been placed on the impact of eWOM (Cantalops and Silva, 2014), confirming customers' independence when they make reviews and its relevance as an information source (Yan

and Tang, 2019). However, the relationship between eWOM and price has been recently considered in price modeling. Thereby they may provide misleading notions of the influence of clients' experience (Tsao et al., 2015). It has been incorporated into hedonic price models (HPM) as a room rating (Zhang et al., 2011b), as hotel online ratings (Ivanov and Piddubna, 2016), or as a hotel reputational measure (Abrate and Viglia, 2016).

Finally, regarding the generalization of results, hotel pricing research has focused on selection available in a city (Abrate and Viglia, 2016; Pawlicz and Napierala, 2017), type of city (Abrate et al., 2012; Baldassin et al., 2017), or a particular country (Becerra et al., 2013). However, tourism environments and markets differ across cities and countries, ultimately influencing management decisions and strategies. In fact, the sequence of the implementation of standards in the hotel industry also vary depending on the country (Zeng et al., 2007), and there are differences in hotel management related to property management, offer and hotel category (Pine and Phillips, 2005). This factor should be considered to avoid results that may distort real patterns.

These factors, apart from adding relevance to research on pricing, increase the use of price in hotel marketing decisions, which in turn causes a predictable increase in price variability. These results contradict the evidence that price instability has a negative effect on hotel profitability, i.e. Tisdell's model (Chen and Chang, 2012).

Tourism decision-making process requires considering different variables from decision areas that interact simultaneously and make it possible to adequately understand variations between prices offered by hotels (Abrate and Viglia, 2016). However, effects on hotel price vary across different price levels (Hung et al., 2010; Masiero et al., 2015). Therefore, hotels attributes and tourist experiences, coupled with country differences and competences, require flexible models which adequately describe heterogeneity for hotel level pricing practices. Quantile regression is applied to contrast whether the effects of the independent variables over hotel price are not constant; its use is especially recommendable for asymmetric variables and distributions with long tails (Koenker and Bassett, 1978), where the ordinary least squares (OLS) method may result in erroneous estimates.

Therefore, our study aims to provide several contributions. Firstly, since hotel price variations require considering different decision areas that interact simultaneously (Abrate and Viglia, 2016), determinants are combined from perspectives of customer, hotel, competition and hotel country, thereby enhancing partial models. Secondly, the effect of hotel category is evaluated for different price levels and countries. Thirdly, from the assumptions of CPT, evidence is provided of the competitive effects of spatial concentration on price. Fourthly, our work seeks to fulfill the need to expand studies on the effect of eWOM on pricing decisions (Cantallops and Silva, 2014). Finally, with the purpose of providing a general approach to hotel pricing studies, our work applies quantile regression, allowing non-constant effects of the determinants, and with a large sample data set (3,800 hotels) from different cities in four EU countries with substantial tourist activity.

2. Literature review

2.1. Hotel room pricing models

Hedonic models (Rosen, 1974) have been the most widely-used approach to explain hotel prices. Anyway, models of competition (Becerra et al., 2013) or monopolistic models based on cost (Van Dijk and Van der Stelt-Steele, 1993) have also been considered. Basic

contribution of HPMs is to provide evidences on the importance of each hotel attribute for income generation, mostly through regression analysis (Masiero et al., 2015). Results obtained have confirmed the effect of both age and restaurant availability (Bull, 1994), category (Becerra et al., 2013; Israeli, 2002), type of location (Espinet et al., 2003), chain affiliation (Becerra et al., 2013; Israeli, 2002), parking availability (Espinet et al., 2003), hotel size (Zhang et al., 2011a), room size or spa availability (Abrate and Viglia, 2016), hotel facilities and technological resources available (Chen and Rothschild, 2010), staff size (Hung et al., 2010; Chen and Chiu, 2014) and customer evaluation of service quality (Zhang et al., 2011b) (see review in Table 1).

The extension of pure HPMs has been developed by incorporating new attributes based on the customers themselves (Thrane, 2007), such as user-perceived quality (Chen and Chiu, 2014), advanced booking effects (Abrate et al., 2012) or the different types of eWOM (Abrate and Viglia, 2016; Pawlicz and Napierala, 2017; Zhang et al., 2011b). Other approaches, such as differentiation or competition effects, have been marginal (Becerra et al., 2013), and, moreover, the application of models that allow non-constant effects on price has been even less frequent. Only Hung et al. (2010) have applied HPM based on quantile regression from a supply perspective, while Masiero et al. (2015) have also applied this model from the demand side.

From a methodological point of view, some of the common features utilized in previous studies include the exploration of the lodging industry in specific locations and the generalized use of the OLS method, which assumes constant effect of pricing determinants. The OLS method requires initial assumptions and non-fulfillment may result in less efficient estimates. Indeed if the conditional distribution of the dependent variable is asymmetric, the assumption of normal error terms is not guaranteed, implying a risk of undesirable estimations. Other methodological alternatives, when the non-fulfillment of OLS assumptions occurs, include geographically weighted regression (Zhang et al., 2011a) and a time series related estimation method (Lee, 2011).

In relation to the generalization of management implications, most studies have focused on hotels from a specific geographic area (city or country). Abrate et al. (2012) propose an HPM based on data from eight European capital cities, focusing on the analysis of pricing strategies. Baldassin et al. (2017) study determinants of prices in twenty six European cities with a two-step estimation procedure, finding differences in terms of cost and quality.

Research setting	Analytical model	Dependent variables	External factors	Internal factors	Researchers
One location (city, town..)	Linear, quadratic, semilog and loglinear hedonic analysis	Room rate	Location	Ranking stars, age, restaurant	Bull (1994)
	Linear hedonic analysis, Semilog hedonic analysis or loglinear hedonic analysis	Room rate	Location	Chain, beds, amenities	Thrane (2007)
				Ranking stars , chain, room size, amenities	Chen and Rothschild (2010)
				Ranking stars , chain, number of rooms	Pawlicz and Napierala (2017)
		Online reviews, booking time, weekend, competence	Ranking stars , number of rooms, , average occupancy, free cancellation, amenities	Abrate and Viglia (2016)	
	Average room rate	Location	Category, cleanliness, number of rooms, amenities	Zhang et al. 2011a)	
	Category stars, number of rooms, year	Zhang et al. (2011b)			
Multiple equation model	Peak season price and off-peak price	Location	Ranking stars, number services, number rooms, brand, presence guidebook, quality certification, amenities	Abrate et al. (2011)	
Linear, quadratic, semilog and loglinear hedonic analysis	Room rate	Location	Chain, AAA rate, amenities	Wu (1999)	
One country (different cities, towns,..)	Linear, quadratic, semilog and loglinear hedonic analysis Random-effect hedonic price model, SEM, latent growth curve models	Room rate Average monthly daily room rate	Location Temperature, interstate location, and specialization of the local economy	Ranking stars, brand	Israeli (2002))
				Ranking stars, establishment variables, hotel style, amenities, contextual Attributes	Soler et al. (2019)
				Amenities	White and Mulligan (2002)
		Town,location	Ranking stars , establishment variables, amenities	Espinet et al. (2003)	
		Geographical distance, number competitors	Ranking stars, room discount, size, age, chain, type of hotel	Becerra et al. (2013)	
		Real gross domestic product , exchange, visitor arrivals, consumer price index, location	Occupancy, chain, service quality, room size, amenities	Chen and Chiu (2014)	
		Average room rate	Market condition, location	Establishment variables, chain, resort, foreign travellers, housekeeping staff per room	Hung et al. (2010)
	Monthly room price	Town, climate	Ranking stars , establishment variables, amenities	Coenders et al. (2003)	
Time series (GARCH)	Room rate	Total tourist arrivals, terrorist attacks, industrial production	Not applicable	Lee (2011)	
Different countries and different cities	Linear, quadratic, semilog and loglinear hedonic analysis	Room rate	Score, location, environment, booking day and time effects	Ranking stars, size, brand, cancelation, star rating, booking day, city as dummy available services	Abrate et al. (2012) Baldassin et al. (2017)

Table 1. Empirical models of hotel room price in selected publications

1 2.2 *Hotel ranking stars*

2 Star category is one of the most commonly used variables in hotel pricing models (Table
3 1) and verifies its positive effect on price (Bull, 1994 and Israeli, 2002). This is the
4 indicator of services and quality offered by hotels (Pawlicz and Napiella, 2017). It has
5 traditionally been considered the key explanatory variable of room price (Bull, 1994,
6 Israeli, 2002), even the most influential (Espinet et al., 2002, Zhang et al., 2011), showing
7 a highly consistent effect for different channels (Tso and Law, 2005). In addition, a high
8 category is usually associated with greater affiliation to quality programs and better
9 physical attributes (Abrate et al., 2011). Even hotel category is an influential factor in
10 dynamic pricing strategies because high category allows maintaining stable prices when
11 the general price trend is decreasing and also allows a more pronounced increase when
12 the trend is rising (Abrate et al., 2012). Likewise, hotel category makes it possible to
13 reduce negative effects of competitive rivalry on prices (Becerra et al., 2013).

14 These studies implicitly make assumptions based on Signaling Theory (Spence, 1973)
15 since potential customers utilize hotel category as a signal to choose desired
16 accommodation to fit their preferences, inducing to a positive relationship between
17 category on price. However, hotels has traditionally been considered as an example of
18 information asymmetries, questioning category as a signal for the consumer and requiring
19 counteracting mechanisms (Akerlof, 1970). Furthermore, Signaling Theory conditions
20 may not always be fulfilled. Thus, the assumption of pay off transparency constitutes an
21 important criticism against signaling models (Kirmani and Rao, 2000), mainly because
22 tourists have much less information about future prices and availability than service
23 providers (Chen and Schwartz, 2006). Similarly, as for one-time tourists with limited
24 access to word-of-mouth, relying on repeated bookings may not be suitable (Wolinsky,
25 1983).

26 It has also been found that ranking by quality does not correspond to ranking by categories
27 (López-Fernández and Serrano-Bedia, 2004). Though official star classification is
28 considered a good quality indicator, there is also significant quality overlapping between
29 adjacent official categories. More specifically, different local and national regulations for
30 hotel categorization are a source of heterogeneity that deteriorates its value as a standard
31 quality signal (Nuñez-Serrano et al., 2014). Further, Nicolau and Sellers (2010) consider
32 that hotels seek additional signals other than category from third parties to communicate
33 their quality.

34 2.3. *Hotels competence*

35 Evidence on competition effects on hotel price indicates that room price increases when
36 room availability among direct competitors decreases (Abrate et al., 2012). From the
37 Industrial Organization perspective, Becerra et al. (2013) find a negative relationship
38 between hotel concentration and hotel prices. However, they use vertical differentiation
39 strategies based on category, finding that competition interacts with category, which
40 reduce the negative effect of competitive rivalry on prices.

41 In contrast, the CPT (King, 1984) posits a positive relationship between the size of the
42 selection of tourist activities available in a place and the economic impact on each one
43 (Daniels, 2007), based on the logic that hotels tend to be located close to each other to
44 increase supply, improve efficiency and survive (Barros, 2005, Yang et al., 2012). By
45 applying this view, the positive relationship between agglomeration degree and hotel's
46 benefit has been supported (Chung and Kalnins, 2001, Canina and Harrison, 2005).
47 Furthermore, given that the existence of hotels in an area may increase the attractiveness
48 of the location, nor the type of hotel establishments located in a certain location, nor the

49 intensity of their agglomeration will necessarily be the same for all price levels, being
50 useful to know the effects of competition for different price levels.

51 In contrast, approaches to competence based on aggregation posit a positive relationship
52 between the size of the selection of tourist activities available in a place and the economic
53 impact on each one. Specifically, CPT (King, 1984) describes patterns of business
54 location in cities, so that larger urban places would have the larger offer of services. The
55 theory assumes that both individuals and businesses are rational. Also, it is assumed that
56 a "service would not be produced and sold if a profit could not be realized" (King, 1984,
57 30). Further, market areas are determined by the range between the minimum demand to
58 break even and the maximum distance a customer would travel to obtain the service
59 (Daniels, 2007). Every market –i.e., central place, is characterized by a specific offer and
60 economies (Derudder and Witlox, 2004). Then, it is expected an agglomeration effect
61 since activities are prone to cluster together in specific locations (King, 1984). Tourism
62 research evidences the existence of external economies of scale (e.g., specialized
63 suppliers in tourism), feeding a cumulative cycle that reinforces the size of the market
64 area.

65 For this context, hotels tend to be located close to each other to increase supply, improve
66 efficiency and survive (Barros, 2005, Yang et al., 2012). By applying this theory, the
67 positive relationship between agglomeration degree and hotel's benefit has been
68 supported (Chung and Kalnins, 2001, Canina and Harrison, 2005). Furthermore, given
69 that the existence of hotels in an area may increase the attractiveness of the location, nor
70 the type of hotel establishments located in a certain location, nor the intensity of their
71 agglomeration will necessarily be the same for all price levels, which is why it is useful
72 to know the effects of competition for different hotel price levels. Though the theory is
73 not exempt of critics, advocates claim its rationality to explain tourism location decisions
74 (Daniels, 2007).

75 *2.4. Electronic Word of Mouth*

76 Online tourism marketing channels have experienced faster growth than other channels,
77 with approximately one fifth of reservations being generated entirely online (Stangl et al.,
78 2016). As a result, the Internet has produced a change of tourist behaviour, providing a
79 high influence of eWOM on hotel industry and consumers (Cantalops and Salvi, 2014).

80 eWOM is a key determinant of consumer decisions (Duan et al., 2008), and its influence
81 is particularly notable in the restaurant and hospitality industries (e.g., Ye et al., 2009).
82 Evidence shows that the effect of eWOM on price can be as important as hotel category
83 (Pawlicz and Napierala, 2017), and in dynamic pricing contexts, eWOM (as online
84 reputation according to Tsang and Prendergast, 2009) is even more important than hotel
85 category (Abrate and Viglia, 2016).

86 Consumer opinion offers greater confidence than communications from a company itself
87 (Vermeulen and Seegers, 2009). Even a numerical rating generates more reliability to
88 prospective customers who are willing to pay more for products with a high rating
89 (Nielsen, 2012). In addition, the publication of ratings and customer comments on tourist
90 accommodation company websites is used by these same businesses to change their prices
91 (Yacouel and Fleischer, 2012, Ögüt and Onur, 2012).

92 From the empirical studies of the effects of eWOM on hoteliers' decisions, it has been
93 found that for those online intermediaries with a positive reputation, the information
94 provided by their customers generates a hotel price premium (Yacouel and Fleischer,
95 2012). The positive effect of eWOM on hotel occupancy (Viglia et al., 2016) and

96 willingness to pay premium prices for accommodation (Nieto-García et al., 2017) have
 97 also been evidenced. Thus, it is clear that opinions published about a hotel can be a
 98 determining factor in hotel pricing.

99 *2.5. Country location*

100 From a management point of view, behavioral decision making varies across different
 101 countries (Laurent, 1983). Thus, the importance of market factors has been highlighted to
 102 explain differences in productivity between countries (Jones and Romer, 2009), diversity
 103 in the success factors of Total Quality Management (Sila and Ebrahimpour, 2003), and
 104 differences in business management styles and how those differences generate variations
 105 in productivity (Bloom and Van Reenen, 2010).

106 In hotel management research, the quality signals in each country that can influence hotel
 107 prices have been identified (Abrate et al., 2011). Several works have revealed the
 108 existence of differences in hotel management in terms of property management (Pine and
 109 Phillips, 2005), human, cultural, market, social and labor management resources between
 110 countries (Nankervis and Debrah, 1995). Also, Lee (2011) shows that there are attributes
 111 associated with the country, such as economic performance or total inbound tourists, that
 112 affect hotel pricing. Even, the city of destination influences hotel rates (Abrate et al. 2012;
 113 Baldassin et al., 2017).

114 **3. Methodology**

115 *3.1. Research setting*

116 The research covers four European countries with thriving tourism activity: France,
 117 Spain, Italy and the United Kingdom. In all of them, the tourism industry contributes
 118 significantly to the country economies, but the greatest contribution occurs in Spain
 119 (Table 2).

	International tourist arrivals	International tourism inbound receipts (US \$ Millions)	Average receipts per arrival (US \$)	Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index
France	84,451,621	45,920	543.7	2 nd
Spain	68,521,255	56,468	824.1	1 st
Italy	50,731,770	39,449.2	777.6	8 th
UK	34,435,840	45,463.6	1,320.2	5 th

120 **Table 2.**

121 Key Indicators in tourism industry

122 Source: UNWTO (2018) and World Economic Forum 2017

123 *3.2. Data collection and variables*

124 The database was built with a combination of web analysis techniques with data from the
 125 information system of international Group Travel Agencies (GTA) (Becerra et al., 2013,
 126 Paulizt and Napierala, 2017). Thus, an initial sample of 14,772 hotels was obtained from
 127 the four countries considered. Finally, due to the existence of missing data in the initial
 128 database, the sample was reduced to 3,800 hotels located in 163 cities and organized in
 129 1,221 commercial zones defined by the GTA. Since the final sample covers geographical
 130 areas of different sizes, the commercial zone was considered as a geographical
 131 competition area because the hotels located within each zone are considered
 132 commercially homogeneous within their category.

133 The information from the GTA provides greater advantages for its comparability,
134 homogeneity and breadth (Abrate and Viglia, 2016, Paulizt and Napierala, 2017). In this
135 case, we have selected the GTA: Veturis.com, which has recently been included in the
136 “1000 Companies to inspire Europe” (London Stock Exchange Group 2017). With
137 bounce rate, page views/user and time on site (minutes) as a references (www.alexa.com,
138 accessed 2 July 2018), Veturis’s bounce rate is lower than that of the most popular OTAs
139 and its page view/user and time on site are only lower than those of booking.com.
140 Similarly, Veturis tops Google searches in real time ranking through keywords such as
141 ‘travel agency’ and ‘tourism intermediaries, remaining ahead of its competition
142 (www.serprobot.com).

143 Additionally, the information about price and hotel attributes included in the sample was
144 retrieved from the hotel websites (Paulizt & Napierala, 2017).

145 Since room price may experience variations caused by the distribution channel, the season
146 or the holding of commercial events, in accordance with previous studies (Hung *et al.*
147 2010, Zhang *et al.*, 2011b), the average room rate for a standard double room is considered
148 herein as a dependent variable. Furthermore, a semi-logarithmic model (Rosen, 1974)
149 was used to describe the impact of the explanatory variables on price. Specifically, the
150 explanatory variables were defined as follows:

- 151 • **Hotel category.** This variable is represented by five dummy variables for the five
152 common star categories (from one to five stars), and the category “Other” used as the
153 reference (Masiero *et al.*, 2015).
154
- 155 • **Hotel local competition.** Two variables are used to represent a hotel’s competence
156 level (Becerra *et al.*, 2013), which ideally should incorporate several dimensions of
157 spatial competition. The first variable, N_Hotels, measures the concentration effect
158 of the area and is computed as the total number of hotels with the same category in
159 the same commercial area. The second, Distance, describes the intensity of
160 agglomeration and is estimated as the average distance of each hotel from all other
161 hotels in its area. For this purpose, the geographical distance between competitors in
162 the same commercial area was calculated using their GPS coordinates and with
163 routines programmed in R. Thus, the resulting variable measures (km), the average
164 distance of a hotel with respect to the other hotels with the same category in its area
165 (Becerra *et al.*, 2013). The consistency of the values obtained was checked and
166 verified.
167
- 168 • **eWOM.** A reputational approach, based on Zhang *et al.* (2011b) was used. This
169 variable measures the average valuation made by the customers of each hotel. This
170 rating made by the customers and published on the web portal is a numerical valuation
171 between zero (the worst evaluation) and ten (the best evaluation).
172
- 173 • **Country.** Dummy variables were used to incorporate hotels countries. More
174 specifically, said dummy variables we considered for France, Italy and UK.
175 Therefore, Spain was considered as the reference country.

176 In addition to the independent variables above, we also included the following control
177 variables:

- 178 • **Hotel size.** We controlled for hotel size using the number of rooms in every hotel. It
179 is expected a significant effect on room price (Becerra *et al.*, 2013).

- 180 • **Hotel type.** We controlled for hotel type identifying the different type of lodgings in
 181 the setting analyzed (aparthotel, hostel, hotels and other types of establishments) by
 182 three dummy variables with the last category used as the reference. These variables
 183 capture objectively the types and level of services and amenities of the hotel.
 184 • **City hotel.** Since there are significant differences on price between city hotels and
 185 hotels located outside urban areas (Falk and Hagsten 2015), this dummy variable was
 186 used to control location effect.

187 Descriptive statistics are contained in Appendix A.

188 3.3. Data analysis

189 In order to analyze what characteristics can influence room prices, the proposed
 190 regression model is given by:

$$191 \quad LNPRICE = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_i Z_i + \sum_{i=1}^5 \gamma_i S_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \omega_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^5 \theta_i C_i$$

192 where C_i denotes the control variables, Z_i the country dummy variables, S_i the category
 193 dummy variables, X_i the continuous variables (eWOM, N_Hotels, Distance). The
 194 coefficient ω_i of a continuous variable, multiplied by 100, provides the percentage of
 195 influence on room price, whereas for a dummy variable (coefficients β_i, γ_i) the percentage
 196 effect on room price is computed by $100 \cdot (e^{\beta_i} - 1)$ (Halvorsen and Palmquist, 1980).

197 The statistical analyses included in this study were obtained using the statistical software
 198 R version 3.3.2 and the package ‘quantreg’ (Koenker, 2017).

199 Table 3 shows the main descriptive statistics of continuous variables, while Table 4 shows
 200 the hotel distribution by category and country.

201

	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
LNPRICE	4.303	0.503	4.210	3.018	7.110
eWOM	7.431	1.208	7.600	0.200	10
N_Hotels	24.84	50.763	7	1	331
Distance	1.728	2.017	1.170	0	25.95

202

Table 3.

203

Sample descriptive statistics.

204

Category\Country	France	Spain	Italy	UK
1*	1.372	3.689	1.780	1.967
2*	24.871	12.466	6.825	8.852
3*	49.399	34.447	37.092	37.377
4*	21.612	43.534	47.181	46.885
5*	0.857	3.417	3.561	4.590
Others hotel establishments	1.887	2.447	3.561	0.328

205

Table 4.

206

Hotels distribution by category and country (%)

207 Firstly, we analysed the existence of endogeneity issues related to reputation variable
 208 (eWOM) by using different sets of instrumental variables (see analysis in Appendix B).
 209 After reviewing literature about eWOM, the instrumental variables considered in the
 210 different sets are Age of hotel, Ecological hotel (Kim et al., 2017), Dinner à la carte (Gu
 211 and Ryan, 2008), Availability of terrace in room, and Entertainment activities (Fernandes
 212 and Fernandes, 2018). Following Semadeni et al. (2014), the effectiveness of endogeneity
 213 tests depends on instrumental quality (strong and exogenous instruments). The F test for
 214 weak instruments rejected, in all cases, the null hypothesis of weak instruments at the one
 215 percent level. Additionally, the Sargan test confirmed that the instruments are exogenous
 216 in all cases. Finally, in all cases the Wu-Hausman test shows that there are no endogeneity
 217 issues related to the variable eWOM.

218 Next, we tested the existence of multicollinearity using the variance inflation factor (VIF).
 219 VIF values for all independent variables are below 2.1, so no multicollinearity was
 220 detected. Next, we considered the estimation of the regression model by applying OLS.
 221 Shapiro-Wilk and Shapiro-France tests confirmed the non-normality of the residuals. In
 222 addition, the Breusch-Pagan test (Hung et al., 2010) shows heterocedasticity in the model.

223 Thus, the OLS assumptions are not satisfied and consequently the OLS estimators may
 224 be less efficient. Moreover, the maximum average room price is sixty times higher than
 225 the minimum average room price for the sample, which suggests asymmetry of the hotel
 226 price distribution. The asymmetry is confirmed by a positive skewness value of 5.96.
 227 Based on these reasons, we considered the use of quantile regression, which is an
 228 appropriate method of estimation with asymmetric variables and long-tail distributions
 229 because it considers a weighted sum of absolute residuals and its estimates are robust to
 230 outliers (Koenker and Bassett, 1978). Furthermore, quantile regression estimates the
 231 conditional quantile functions and makes it possible to analyze whether a specific
 232 independent variable has a different effect on the conditional distribution of the dependent
 233 variable. Thus, quantile regression provides a full representation of conditional
 234 distribution.

235

236 The quantile regression model is given by:

$$237 \quad y_i = x_i' \beta_\theta + u_{\theta i}$$

238 where $\theta \in (0,1)$ is the quantile, y_i the dependent variable, x_i a vector of explanatory
 239 variables, $u_{\theta i}$ the residuals vector and β_θ the vector of parameters to be estimated. Then,
 240 so that $\text{Quant}_\theta(y_i | x_i) = x_i' \beta_\theta$ by minimization of

$$241 \quad \min_{\beta} \sum_{y_i \geq x_i \beta_\theta} \theta |y_i - x_i \beta_\theta| + \sum_{y_i < x_i \beta_\theta} (1 - \theta) |y_i - x_i \beta_\theta|$$

242 To estimate this, we considered the Frisch-Newton method (Portnoy and Koenker, 1997)
 243 and applied the Feng et al. (2011) bootstrap method to obtain standard errors estimates
 244 for the parameters.

245 For the goodness of fit for quantile regression, we considered the Wald test proposed in
 246 Koenker and Bassett (1982b) and the pseudo R^2 value defined in Koenker and Machado
 247 (1999).

248

249 **4. Results**

250 Figure 1 shows the effect of each explanatory variable throughout the price distribution
 251 (from quantile 0.01 to 0.99). The solid horizontal line at zero represents the null effect.

252 The dashed horizontal lines with the solid line represent OLS estimate. The shaded region
 253 is a 95% point-wise confidence band for quantile regression coefficients.

254
 255 **Figure 1.**

256 Estimated coefficients with quantile regression for room price (by quantile)

257 To analyze the influence of explanatory variables throughout the price distribution, it is
 258 common to estimate using quantile regression at the 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th
 259 percentiles of the distribution of the dependent variable (Masiero et al., 2015). Figure 1
 260 shows variables (France, Italy and Distance) whose effect at the 1st percentile is different
 261 with respect to the 10th percentile, as it also displays other variables (France, UK,
 262 N_Hoteles) whose effect at the 99th percentile is different with respect to the 90th
 263 percentile. Therefore, we included the results at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

264 Table 5 shows the coefficients estimated by OLS and quantile regression at the considered
 265 percentiles. Additionally, Table 5 provides the pseudo R2 value and the Wald test (F-
 266 statistic) proposed in Koenker and Bassett (1982b). The Wald test contrasts if the full
 267 model is significant respect to the model with only control variables. Results reveal that
 268 the full model is significant in all cases.

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	OLS	Quantile						
		0.01	0.1	0.25	0.5	0.75	0.9	0.99
Intercept	3.745***	2.982***	3.225***	3.412**	3.703***	4.034**	4.262***	4.394***
France	0.517***	0.261***	0.359***	0.475**	0.566***	0.624**	0.599***	0.287**
Italy	0.030	-0.143**	4.8E-3	0.019	-0.021	0.019	0.067	0.343***
UK	0.678***	0.431***	0.516***	0.617**	0.706***	0.859**	0.882***	0.275
eWOM	0.046***	0.056***	0.048***	0.055**	0.054***	0.043**	0.040***	0.046
1*	-0.426***	0.017	-0.152	-	-0.294***	-	-0.451***	0.018
				0.289**		0.538**		
2*	-0.381***	0.130*	-0.093	-	-0.289**	-	-0.371**	0.030
				0.286**		0.526**		
3*	-0.246**	0.220**	0.015	-0.137	-0.153	-	-0.176	0.075
						0.357**		
4*	-0.012	0.404***	0.219	0.046	0.077	-0.117	0.079	0.324
5*	0.524***	0.836***	0.589***	0.512**	0.595***	0.562**	0.772***	0.666**
N_Hotels	1.2E-3***	9.8E-4***	8.5E-4***	1.1E-3***	1.7E-3***	2.2E-3***	1.8E-3***	-2.9E-3***
Distance	-0.016***	-3.8E-3	-0.022***	-	-0.023***	-	-6.7E-3	-0.019
				0.025**		0.024**		
Hotel Size	2.9E-4***	4.9E-6	2.7E-4***	2.5E-4***	2.1E-4**	2.3E-4**	4.2E-4**	6.8E-4
Aparthotel	0.407***	-0.271*	0.120	0.257**	0.171*	0.403**	0.409**	1.640***
Hostel	0.076	-0.330*	-0.122	-0.040	-0.045	0.187	0.014	-0.250
Hotel	0.194**	-0.172*	0.090	0.159	0.037	0.199*	0.010	0.751**
City Hotel	-0.010	0.030	6.9E-3	5.1E-4	0.4E-4	-0.025	-0.038	-0.276**
R ²	0.388	0.178	0.192	0.221	0.259	0.284	0.275	0.139
F, H ₀ :β _i =0	179.94**	40.812**	64.846**	130.2**	152.28**	146.3**	110.14**	10.885**

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

277 **Table 5.**
278 Regression coefficients with OLS and quantile regression.

279

280 The OLS results show that all variables, except Italy and 4*, have a significant effect on
281 price. Coefficients for category confirm a positive effect of hotel category on price, that
282 is, higher hotel category implies higher price. The results show that “Other hotel
283 establishments” have a similar price to four-star hotels, significantly higher than one-star,
284 two-stars and three-stars hotels (34.69%, 31.68% and 21.81% respectively) and
285 significantly lower than five-star hotels (68.88%). For country variables, results show that
286 Spanish and Italian hotels have similar prices while France and UK have a significantly
287 higher price than Spain or Italy (67.70% and 96.99%, respectively). The variable eWOM
288 has a positive effect on price, meaning an incremental point in the valuation of a hotel

289 increases the room price by 4.6%. Finally, the positive effect of the variable N_hotels on
 290 price combined with the negative impact of the variable Distance confirm that hotel
 291 concentration has a positive relationship with room price.

292 The quantile regression results show that each explanatory variable is significant at some
 293 of the quantiles considered, emphasizing France, 5* and N_Hotels with significant effect
 294 at all quantiles. Furthermore, Wald test for slope equality (Koenker and Bassett 1982a)
 295 shows that the effect of all independent variables differs across quantiles, except for 5*,
 296 whose impact is constant over the conditional distribution of the room price (Table 6).

297

	0.01, 0.1	0.1, 0.25	0.25, 0.5	0.5, 0.75	0.75, 0.9	0.9,0.99
France	7.6E-3***	1.5E-6***	5.3E-5***	9.2E-3***	0.261	1.6E-3***
Italy	0.029**	0.653	0.036**	0.177	0.277	0.205
UK	0.427	7.0E-3***	0.011**	8.5E-6***	0.573	5.4E-6***
eWOM	0.408	0.218	0.879	0.076*	0.676	0.732
1*	0.809	0.377	0.917	0.017**	0.684	0.451
2*	0.748	0.195	0.997	0.018**	0.463	0.308
3*	0.769	0.317	0.800	0.043**	0.397	0.601
4*	0.790	0.253	0.630	0.054*	0.357	0.604
5*	0.723	0.644	0.287	0.805	0.360	0.845
N_Hotels	0.646	0.092*	8.1E-4***	2E-3***	0.245	2.8E-5***
Distance	1.3E-4***	0.283	0.629	0.815	3.4E-3***	0.570

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

298 **Table 6.**

299 Wald test, significant differences of slope among quantiles

300

301 The category coefficients estimated with quantile regression and Figure 1 both display
 302 the positive effect of the hotel category. Similarly, non-category establishments (i.e., no
 303 stars) have similar prices to one-star hotels and are significantly positioned below all other
 304 categories at the 1st percentile. For all quantiles, these hotels display prices significantly
 305 lower than five-star hotels, in some cases similar to the rest of categories (10th and 90th),
 306 or similar to the three-star and four-star hotels (25th, 50th and 90th) or only similar to
 307 four-star hotels (75th).

308 For country variables, results show that French hotels display a significantly higher price
 309 than Spanish hotels at all quantiles. The same goes for British hotels, except at the 99th
 310 percentile, where British and Spanish prices are similar. The difference between French
 311 and British prices with respect to Spanish price varies across quantiles (Table 6).
 312 Furthermore, Italian hotels have significantly lower prices than Spanish hotels at the 1st
 313 percentile (13.32%) while Italian prices are higher than Spanish prices at the 99th
 314 percentile (40.92%). Generally, UK hotels have the highest price at all quantiles, but the
 315 highest price is from Italy at the 99th percentile.

316 eWOM has a significant positive effect on room price except at the 99th percentile. Table
 317 6 displays a non-constant impact of eWOM throughout the price distribution. Finally,
 318 regarding competition, the variable N_Hotels has a significantly non-constant effect,

319 displaying a positive relationship with price except at the 99th percentile, where the effect
320 is negative. The variable Distance has a non-constant effect throughout the price
321 distribution, with a significant negative effect on price at all quantiles, except at 1st, 90th
322 and 99th percentiles. Thus, the concentration–price relationship is positive, except at the
323 99th percentile, where a lower number of competitors results in higher prices.

324 **5. Conclusions**

325 Based on a sample data set of 3,800 hotels in four European countries, this paper analyzes
326 the influence of hotel category, country of location, eWOM received by hotel customers
327 and hotel spatial competence by modeling hotel price through OLS and quantile
328 regression. Data have been obtained through a multisource procedure.

329 It must be noted that there are differential effects for all explanatory variables except for
330 five-star category. For all quantiles, estimations provide support to the positive effect of
331 the category on the price, verifying the heterogeneity of the effect. Furthermore, hotels
332 included in ‘Other hotel establishments’ offer a similar price to the three and four-star
333 price at certain price levels. The case of 5-star hotels proves to be unique in that only the
334 category is linked to the price when the latter is very high. Even more, a particularly
335 different behavior is revealed at the 99th percentile with respect to the rest of quantiles.

336 The effect of eWOM is significant, revealing eWOM as an explanatory variable in all the
337 quantiles/price levels, with a significant effect (except for the 99th percentile).

338 Results also confirm the significant effect of hotel country location and show the
339 competitiveness in prices of hotels in Spain and Italy, compared to hotels located in
340 France and the UK. The highest prices correspond, at all price levels except the 99th
341 percentile, to the UK, followed by the hotel prices in France, while Spanish and Italian
342 hotels only present price differences at the 1st percentile. Italian hotels are more
343 competitive than Spanish hotels, with the exception of the 99th percentile, where Spanish
344 hotels have lower prices. These results suggest that there is a high quality/price ratio
345 attributed to hotel country location and that European destinations located in Western
346 Europe (France, the UK) tend to be more expensive than destinations in Southern Europe
347 (Spain, Italy), with the exception of the 99th percentile, where Italian hotels display the
348 most expensive prices. This result is consistent with an external hotel price index such as
349 the one provided by Deloitte-STR Global and Smith Travel Research Inc. (2017), which
350 measures average room rates calculated for first-class branded hotels.

351 **6. Discussion**

352 A first contribution of this study is to extend pure hedonic models focused on hotel
353 attributes and amenities, or that do not contemplate differentiated effects over price
354 distribution. Quantile regression estimation is justified especially in the presence of an
355 asymmetric dependent variable, allowing the identification of heterogeneous effects
356 throughout the distribution.

357 Another interesting contribution is related to the link between country location and price
358 competitiveness. Specific country factors are to be considered to account for differences
359 in prices for hotels with similar categories.

360 Regarding the effect of eWOM, it should be noted that the large sample used in the study
361 and the full range of hotels covered contribute to overcoming previous studies (Yen and
362 Tang, 2019).

363 As theoretical implications, these results confirm the applicability of Signaling Theory
364 but only as a first approach, albeit imprecisely. eWOM is considered as a complementary

365 quality signal to hotel category. These results suggest the existence of information
366 asymmetries and indicate that hoteliers may adopt additional quality signals to justify
367 pricing decisions (Nicolau and Sellers, 2010). Besides, analysis of price as asymmetric
368 variable shows heterogeneity of explicative variables effects, questioning the validity of
369 the Tisdell's model.

370 Concerning the applicability of CPT to hotel pricing, the results of the spatial competence
371 variables confirm its assumptions, though for the 99th quantile is not confirmed, because
372 the price decreases when the number of competitors increases.

373 Hotels could benefit of a location with high concentration of competition, as relationship
374 is positive. Previous studies found a weak negative effect of the number of competitors
375 on the price, therefore suggesting that the number of competitors should not be so decisive
376 (Falk and Hagsten, 2015). Our study confirms evidences that negative effects of
377 competition –reduction in prices, can be compensated with benefits of increasing
378 occupation, which thereby improves hotel performance (Chung and Kalnins, 2001,
379 Canina et al., 2005). It should be noted that for the 99th percentile, the effect of the
380 number of competitors is negative, so location at this price level is preferable in low
381 concentration locations.

382 Some managerial implications can be drawn. Hoteliers should take into account
383 consumers' online assessments, paying special attention to those comments located on
384 third-party websites. Though hotel category is a determinant of the rate, hotels managers
385 should not allocate all their efforts only on obtaining an upgrade of their hotel category,
386 as there are other categories in which price level is similar to three and four-star hotels.

387 Location decisions have considerable consequences for pricing. Commercial zone with
388 other hotels of similar category allows hoteliers to fix higher prices. However, as an
389 exception, results reveal the possible existence of a substitution effect in the high-priced
390 zone, with greater sensitivity. Also, evidences reveals differences in competitiveness
391 between countries, with higher level for Spain and Italy compared to hotels located in
392 France and the UK.

393 It is interesting to note the emergence of sharing economy as source of competition for
394 hotels as research topic. Recent contributions find that while in hotels, category or
395 attributes are essential variables, instead in sharing economy based accommodation host
396 attributes (Wang and Nicolau, 2017), and reputational determinants are the critical
397 variables (Abrate and Viglia, 2017).

398 This paper does feature several limitations that may encourage future research. Firstly,
399 the present study incorporates hotel category and country location, but it would be
400 interesting to consider the existence of regulatory differences to isolate and determine the
401 validity of category as a price signal. Also, country-effect is only considered in the model
402 through dummy variables. It would be interesting to incorporate variables related to
403 cultural, historical or economic factors of each country. Secondly, other countries could
404 be considered in order to obtain the universalization of results. Thirdly, the estimated
405 model incorporates competition through the number of nearby hotels and distance. While
406 this is an alternative and enlightening approach, results obtained should be investigated
407 closely since other evidences in literature contradict the positive effect of the number of
408 competitors on price (Becerra et al 2013). Such findings could indicate that the effect of
409 the number of competitors is non-linear, requiring alternative model specification.
410 Another limitation is related to the static approach of this modeling, in comparison with
411 a dynamic approach based on available room more than hotels per se. Additionally, a
412 future line of research is to determine whether the aggregation of hotels in zones can

413 create shared knowledge and, therefore, be a source of competitive advantage (Pinch et
414 al., 2003). Finally, other measurements of eWOM can be incorporated in order to achieve
415 a generalization of results (Yen and Tang, 2019).

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626 **Appendix A: Sample descriptive statistics.**

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First Price Quartile					
	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
eWOM	7.099	1.113	7	0.200	10
N_Hotels	14.72	44.244	4	1	331
Distance	1.538	1.995	0.915	0	17.890
Second Price Quartile					
	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
eWOM	7.425	1.091	7.6	2	10
N_Hotels	21.75	52.535	5	1	331
Distance	1.748	2.134	1.210	0	25.95
Third Price Quartile					
	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
eWOM	7.569	1.24	7.9	2	10
N_Hotels	28.95	52.627	10	1	331
Distance	1.88	1.966	1.46	0	11.98
Fourth Price Quartile					
	Mean	St. dev.	Median	Min	Max
eWOM	7.632	1.305	7.9	2	10
N_Hotels	33.92	51.156	13	1	268
Distance	1.746	1.958	1.070	0	17.92

629 **Table A.1.**

630 Sample descriptive statistics by price quartile.

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First Price Quartile				
Category\Country	France	Spain	Italy	UK
1*hotels	6.818	7.125	7.792	6.667
2*hotels	47.727	22.85	22.078	33.333
3*hotels	36.363	44.349	48.052	53.333
4*hotels	0	22.604	16.883	6.667
5*hotels	0	0	0	0
Others hotel establishments	9.091	3.071	5.195	0
Second Price Quartile				
Category\Country	France	Spain	Italy	UK
1*hotels	0	3.268	0	11.111
2*hotels	48.718	10.850	2.247	27.778
3*hotels	44.872	37.908	52.810	50
4*hotels	5.128	45.621	40.449	5.556
5*hotels	0	0.392	0	0
Others hotel establishments	1.282	1.961	4.494	5.556
Third Price Quartile				
Category\Country	France	Spain	Italy	UK
1*hotels	1.183	1.309	0	4.478
2*hotels	28.994	5.237	2.913	11.940
3*hotels	48.521	27.823	33.009	62.687
4*hotels	18.343	60.393	59.223	19.403
5*hotels	0.592	3.273	1.942	1.493
Others hotel establishments	2.367	1.964	2.913	0
Fourth Price Quartile				
Category\Country	France	Spain	Italy	UK
1*hotels	1.027	1.039	0	0
2*hotels	12.671	5.195	1.471	4.390
3*hotels	53.082	17.143	10.294	26.829
4*hotels	31.164	56.883	72.059	62.439
5*hotels	1.370	16.883	14.706	6.341
Others hotel establishments	0.685	2.857	1.471	0

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Table A.2.

647

Quartile Hotels distribution by category and country (%)

648 **Appendix B: Endogeneity analysis**

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Diagnostic tests	df1	df2	Statistic	p-value
Weak instruments	2	3782	19.401	4.1E-9***
Sargan	1		0.853	0.356
Wu-Hausman	1	3782	2.366	0.124

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

650 Table B.1: eWOM endogeneity diagnostic with the instrumentals variables Age and Availability of
651 terrace.

Diagnostic tests	df1	df2	statistic	p-value
Weak instruments	3	3781	13.369	1.1E-8***
Sargan	2		3.832	0.147
Wu-Hausman	1	3782	1.719	0.190

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

652 Table B.2: eWOM endogeneity diagnostic with the instrumentals variables Age, Availability of terrace
653 and Ecological Hotel.

654

Diagnostic tests	df1	df2	statistic	p-value
Weak instruments	4	3780	10.027	4.5E-8***
Wu-Hausman	1	3782	1.709	0.191
Sargan	3		4.878	0.181

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

655 Table B.3: eWOM endogeneity diagnostic with the instrumentals variables Age, Availability of terrace,
656 Ecological Hotel and Dinner á la carte.

657

Diagnostic tests	df1	df2	statistic	p-value
Weak instruments	5	3779	8.459	5.7E-8***
Wu-Hausman	1	3782	1.727	0.189
Sargan	4		4.879	0.300

* p<0.1

** p<0.05

*** p<0.01

658 Table B.4: eWOM endogeneity diagnostic with the instrumentals variables Age, Availability of terrace,
659 Ecological Hotel, Dinner á la carte and Entertainment activities.

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